

IPBES TCA Chapter 2. DMR 2.10 Spiritual and religious visions/IPBES transformative change assessment

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Description:

The review corresponds to the IPBES transformative change assessment. The IPBES scoping document for the transformative change assessment describes that chapter 2 should examine the implications of different visions for sectors, sub-systems (including economic/market, financial, political, legal/judicial, educational, Indigenous and local systems, and ecosystems) and the interactions between them, at different spatial scales. In this context, a review and analysis of spiritual and religious visions was conducted to feed the visions database of chapter 2.

Process overview

Protocol

Step 1: Initial selection of classic visions

Type of analysis/search/review: expert search

Search languages: English/Spanish

Date of the search: June-December 2022

Sample extracted: 21 texts (A)

Fields extracted: Identification number, Title, Author, Year, Tradition, Source, Language of accessed version, Text (or example), Supporting information, and Comments.

Location and format of the data:

3-IPBES_TCA_CH2_DMR 2.10_SRV_initial_texts(A).csv

An initial selection of classic texts containing spiritual and religious visions was conducted, using the initial working definition of *vision* of chapter 2: “description of a desired future, which is values-based, usually qualitative, tends to hide risk, is energizing, and functions as trigger of voluntary change. Visions are broadly related to nature or human-nature relations”.

Spirituality was considered as the search for the sacred in oneself, and *religion* as the institutionalisation of such search, which can be compatible or incompatible with spirituality depending on the context (Hill et al., 2000; de Kalbermatten, 2003).

The initial selection started from two texts that were known by the experts: the *Book of Job* from the Old Testament and the poem *Jerusalem* by William Blake (See references).

A search based on expert knowledge was performed to identify additional texts, using four objectives:

1. Include texts that fit chapter 2 definition of *vision* as much as possible. Selected texts should include at least one reference to an element from nature (e.g., garden, tree, fountain, grass, animal, rain, etc). Texts without any reference to an element from nature were considered difficult to relate to current understandings of nature and thus excluded.
2. Cover the widest possible diversity of spiritual and religious traditions, geographical origins and historical periods.
3. Include texts that are as close as possible to the original vision/message, i.e. exclude academic or theological elaborations about spirituality and religion.
4. Do not limit the search to the official interpretation of religious institutions. Both canonical and non-canonical scriptures should be included.

The spreadsheet contains 21 texts from a wide diversity of traditions: Christian mysticism (4), Hinduism (2), Judeo-Christian (2), Gnosticism (1), Jewish mysticism (1), Islam (1), Mystic poetry in Italian (1), Mystic poetry in Persian (1), Mystic poetry in Hindi (1), Mystic poetry in Marathi (1), Mystic poetry in Javanese (1), Mystic poetry in Spanish (1), Mystic poetry in English (1), Romantic/Idealist literature (1), Alchemy (1), and Unknown (1). Even if the original sources were written in several languages, the accessed versions were in English (19) and Spanish (2).

For 13 of the texts the author is known with confidence, whereas for 2 of them the author is known with uncertainty. For 6 texts the author is unknown. Texts range from 6th-5th centuries BC to 1936.

Step 2: Preliminary analysis of classic visions

Type of analysis/search/review: inductive coding and expert knowledge

Date of analysis: December 2022

Sample extracted: 14 texts (B)

Treatment applied:

- A preliminary reading and interpretation of the texts was conducted using the supporting information extracted with the visions (listed under “Supporting information” in database (A)). Common and specific themes emerging from the selected texts were identified, using inductive coding. Inductive coding consists in structuring qualitative data through codes that emerge from the data, i.e., without resorting to pre-defined codes.
- After this analysis, texts with unclear, difficult, or not so inspiring visions for transformative change were removed. 14 visions were retained.
- A list of spiritual and religious traditions absent in the selection was developed to guide snowballing in the successive phase. These traditions are Buddhist, Reformed Christian, Taoist, Jain, Sikh and Zoroastrian.

Location and format of the data:

4-IPBES_TCA_CH2_DMR 2.10_SRV_analysis(B).csv

Step 3: Selection of contemporary visions

Type of analysis/search/review: expert and snowball search

Search languages: English and French

Date of the search: December 2022-March 2023

Sample extracted: 10 texts

A selection of contemporary texts containing spiritual and religious visions was conducted to complement the selection of classic visions. While classic visions were highly inspiring for transformative change and thus very valuable for chapter 2, the experts realized that it was also necessary to capture the response from contemporary spiritual and religious communities to biodiversity loss and nature's decline.

These texts were selected based on knowledge from experts of the assessment and snowball search. Snowball search focused mostly on inter-tradition initiatives. For example, the lists of signatories of two inter-tradition declarations related to biodiversity loss and nature's decline were used to snowball in search for more visions.

Selected texts pertained to the following traditions: Sahaja Yoga, Christian, Catholic, Islamic and inter-tradition.

Step 4: Consolidation of database

Type of analysis/search/review: expert and snowball search

Search languages: English

Date of the search: March 2023-March 2024

Sample extracted: 33 texts

The database containing classic and contemporary spiritual and religious visions was consolidated by:

1. Conducting a snowball search for classic visions aimed at filling the gaps for traditions absent so far. Visions from the following traditions were added: Taoist, Sikh, Buddhist and Zoroastrian.

2. Including additional visions from the Judeo-Christian, Christian and Hindu traditions following suggestions based on expert knowledge from experts of the assessment.
3. Conducting a snowball search for contemporary visions aimed at widening the range of traditions included. Visions from the following traditions were added: Hindu, Zoroastrian and Sikh. A vision from the Bahá'í tradition was added following reviewers' comments.
4. Removing texts that were not very clear or that did not have enough quality information to extract a vision.

A total of 33 spiritual and religious visions was retained for final analysis (20 classic visions and 13 contemporary visions). Retained visions date between the 8th century BCE and 2023. They come from a wide array of spiritual and religious traditions: Judeo-Christian, Christian, Taoist, Buddhist, Hindu, Islamic, Mystic (Italian/Catholic, Spanish/Catholic, Persian/Sufi, Marathi/Hindu, English), Catholic, Sikh, Zoroastrian, Bahá'í, Sahaja Yoga, inter-tradition, alchemy, and other types of literature. The texts used to extract the visions (English translations) were kept in a word document to facilitate qualitative analysis and coding.

Step 5: Coding

Type of analysis/search/review: deductive coding

Date of the analysis: March 2023-March 2024

Sample analysed: 33 texts

All the visions retained were coded using the general coding rule from chapter 2 to feed the visions database.

Location and format of the data:

5-IPBES_TCA_CH2_DMR 2.10_SRV_coding(C).csv

References

Blake, W. (2019). *And did those feet in ancient time*. In: Preface to *Milton* [ca. 1808]. The Complete Poems. Digireads.com Publishing, p. 338.

de Kalbermatten, G. (2003). *The third advent* (1st U.S. ed). daisyamerica LLC.

Hill, P. C., Pargament, K. I., Hood, R. W., McCullough, J., Michael E., Swyers, J. P., Larson, D. B., & Zinnbauer, B. J. (2000). Conceptualizing religion and spirituality : Points of commonality, points of departure. *Journal for the theory of social behaviour*, 30(1), 5177.

Job. In: *King James Bible*, online version. <https://thekingsbible.com/Bible/18/1>

Definition of files

ID	Name	File type	Size	Description
1	1-IPBES_TCA_chapter 2_DMR 2.10_spiritual&religious_visions	pdf	147 Ko	DMR
2	2-IPBES_TCA_CH2_DMR 2.10_SRV_process3	jpg	89 Ko	Process flowchart

3	3-IPBES_TCA_CH2_DMR 2.10_SRV_initial_texts(A).csv	csv	49 Ko	Data(A) initial selection of classic spiritual and religious visions
4	4-IPBES_TCA_CH2_DMR 2.10_SRV_analysis(B).csv	csv	35 Ko	Data(B) refined selection of classic spiritual and religious visions
5	5-IPBES_TCA_CH2_DMR 2.10_SRV_coding(C).csv	csv	77 Ko	Data(C) final selection and coding of classic and contemporary spiritual and religious visions